

**ВПЛИВ ФІТОЗАСОБІВ (ЛИСТЯ І СІК АЛОЕ ТА БЕРЕЗОВИХ БРУНЬОК) НА СТАН
СЛИЗОВОЇ ОБОЛОНКИ ШЛУНКА ТА ДВНАДЦЯТИПАЛОЇ КИШКИ У ХВОРИХ НА
ПЕПТИЧНУ ВИРАЗКУ З АРТЕРІАЛЬНОЮ ГІПЕРТЕНЗІЄЮ І ЦУКРОВИМ ДІАБЕТОМ ТИПУ 2**

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**THE INFLUENCE OF PHYTOPRODUCTS (LEAVES AND JUICE OF ALOE AND BIRCH BURDS)
ON THE STATE OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE STOMACH AND DUODENUM IN
PATIENTS WITH PEPTIC ULCER WITH ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION AND TYPE 2 DIABETES**

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Анотація

У статті висвітлено лікувальні властивості листя і соку алое, що містять у своєму складі вітаміни, ферменти, фітонциди, смолисті речовини, сліди ефірних масел, а також антраглікозиди (алоїн, наталоїн, рабарберон, гомонаталоїн, емодин). У складі листя алое виявлено високий вміст кальцію, барію, селену, стронцію, літію і бору. **В березових бруньках** містяться ефірні масла, смолисті речовини, флавоноїди, сапоніни, сесквітерпенові лактони, фітонциди, вітаміни, аскорбінові кислоти, каротин, флавоноїди, нікотинуву кислоту, дубильні речовини, глікозиди. **А також** - мінеральні речовини (натрій, магній, алюміній, залізо, стронцій, кремній, титан, барій, марганець, нікель, кальцій, мідь, цирконій, калій, фосфор.

Висновок. Оскільки алое та березові бруньки мають великий спектр лікувальних властивостей, а саме, жовчогінну, протизапальну, антисептичну, протиопікову, та одночасно посилює секрецію травних залоз, покращує апетит і травлення, антибактеріальна властивість відносно стафілококів, стрептококів, дифтерійної, черевнотифозної і дизентерійної паличок, дозволяє встановити їх вплив на перебіг пептичної виразки шлунка та дванадцятипалої кишки у поєднанні з артеріальною гіпертензією та цукровим діабетом типу 2.

Abstract

The article highlights the healing properties of aloe leaves and juice, which contain vitamins, enzymes, phytoncides, resinous substances, traces of essential oils, as well as anthraglycosides (aloin, nataloin, rhubarberon, homonataloin, emodin). A high content of calcium, barium, selenium, strontium, lithium and boron was found in the composition of aloe leaves. Birch buds contain essential oils, resinous substances, flavonoids, saponins, sesquiterpene lactones, phytoncides, vitamins, ascorbic acids, carotene, flavonoids, nicotinic acid, tannins, glycosides. And also - minerals (sodium, magnesium, aluminum, iron, strontium, silicon, titanium, barium, manganese, nickel, calcium, copper, zirconium, potassium, phosphorus).

Conclusion. Since aloe and birch buds have a wide range of medicinal properties, namely, choleric, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, anti-burn, and at the same time enhance the secretion of digestive glands, improve appetite and digestion, antibacterial property against staphylococci, streptococci, diphtheria, typhoid and dysentery bacilli, allows to establish their effect on the course of peptic ulcer of the stomach and of the duodenum in combination with arterial hypertension and type 2 diabetes.

Ключові слова: алое, березові бруньки, пептична виразка, шлунок, дванадцятипала кишка, артеріальна гіпертензія, цукровий діабет.

Keywords: aloe, birch buds, peptic ulcer, stomach, duodenum, arterial hypertension, diabetes.

Relevance of the topic. As you know, peptic ulcer gastroenterology. [1,3]. And the influence of H. Pylori, (PE) is one of the most common diseases in modern as the main pathogen, has been proven long ago and

convincingly. However, over time, there have been reports about the immune defense of the host organism, which, together with the factors of the stomach environment, create a high rate of genomic variability of *H. pylori* [2,5], which contributes to the active evolution of the pathogen and its adaptation to its host. Increased HR variability (genes *cagA* and *vacA*) leads to the development of the most serious diseases of the stomach and PPD: atrophic gastritis, peptic ulcer disease, and stomach cancer.

Since ancient times, people have known that watercress has a lot of medicinal properties. This plant is very often used in folk medicine. The roots of the plant contain a lot of essential oil, tannins, alkaloid and glycoside acorin, calamine. Its leaves also contain many tannins and essential oils. This oil consists of a mixture of terpenes and sesquiterpenes, azarylaldehydes, which provides a specific smell. And in the rhizome of the flatbread there is a small amount of fragrant soap, vitamins, protein, starch and minerals. A decoction of this plant can be taken to treat stomach aches. The roots have an effect that increases appetite, perfectly improves digestion, and strengthens the reflex separation of all gastric juice. Today, marsh wort is used in folk medicine as a good remedy for the treatment of peptic ulcers[4,6].

The purpose of the study is the effect of phytoremedies (leaves and juice of aloe and birch buds) on the condition of the mucous membrane of the stomach and duodenum in patients with peptic ulcer with hypertension and type 2 diabetes

Research materials. All patients received inpatient treatment in the gastroenterology department of Chernivtsi Regional Clinical Hospital in 2013-2016. Diagnostics was carried out in accordance with the National recommendations of the Unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care for patients with PVS and DPK in adults, approved by the order of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine No. 613 of the Ministry of Health of Ukraine dated September 3, 2014. Determination of the stage and degree of arterial hypertension (AH) was carried out according to the criteria recommended in 2013 by the European Society of Hypertension (ESH) / European Society of Cardiology (ESC). The diagnosis of type 2 diabetes was established according to WHO standards 2006/2011 ($HbA1c > 6.5\%$, fasting plasma glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/l, postprandial glycemia after 2 hours ≥ 11.0 mmol/l).

Diagnosis was carried out in accordance with the National recommendations of the Unified clinical protocol of primary, emergency and secondary (specialized) medical care for patients with PVS and DPK in adults, approved by the order.

Research results. Aloe leaves and juice contain vitamins, enzymes, phytoncides, resinous substances, traces of essential oils, as well as anthraglycosides (aloin, nataloin, rhubarberon, homonataloin, emodin). Calcium (79.1 mg/g) is the most abundant among macronutrients in leaves, and barium (14.90 $\mu\text{g/g}$), selenium (11.90 $\mu\text{g/g}$), and strontium (17.64 $\mu\text{g/g}$) are among micronutrients. but especially a lot of lithium (162.00 $\mu\text{g/g}$) and boron (94.00 $\mu\text{g/g}$). Medicinal

properties of aloe vera: choleric, increases the secretion of digestive glands, improves appetite and digestion, anti-inflammatory, anti-burn, antibacterial against staphylococci, streptococci, diphtheria, typhoid and dysentery bacilli. Aloe vera juice and extract are widely used for the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases, such as: gastritis and ulcers of the stomach and duodenum, constipation[6,7].

Nowadays, birch is an integral element of the landscaping of our cities and villages and is widely used in the practice of a doctor. Birch buds contain 3-5.5% of essential oils, resinous substances, flavonoids, saponins, sesquiterpene lactones, phytoncides, vitamins. Birch leaves are rich in essential oils (0.05-0.8%), saponins (3.2%), ascorbic acid (2.8%), resinous substances, carotene, flavonoids, nicotinic acid, tannins, glycosides. The most healing in birch is birch sap, which contains a unique set of useful components - sugar (1-4%), minerals (sodium, magnesium, aluminum, iron, strontium, silicon, titanium, barium, manganese, nickel, calcium, copper, zirconium, potassium, phosphorus). The most effective infusions and decoctions of birch buds are diuretic, choleric and antiseptic. Application in the treatment of atherosclerosis, edema of cardiac etiology, anemia, giardiasis, tracheitis and other diseases. Recipe for tincture for stomach ulcers[1,8,9].

Take 50 g of birch buds and pour them with 0.5 l of alcohol, infuse the buds, shaking occasionally, for 3 weeks in a dark place. Then strain the infusion and take 20 drops three times a day 20 minutes before meals. Birch raw materials are used in the production of activated carbon "Carbolene", which effectively absorbs bacterial toxins and poisons, which is used in dysentery, flatulence, spasms, dyspepsia, increased acidity, allergies, atherosclerosis. [1,2,3,10,11,12].

It is known that every year the comorbidity of pathologies occurs more often and, according to the results of a study by D. Campbell-Scherer (2010), is up to 69% in young people, up to 93% in middle-aged patients, and up to 98% in elderly patients. However, the number of multimorbid conditions is also increasing and reaches up to 10% or more among patients of the youth period and up to 80% - among patients of elderly and senile age. Taking into account the identified metabolic disorders (changes in lipid metabolism, glucose, etc.), which are risk factors for the development of endothelial dysfunction [5,13,16,17] and an early prognostic sign in middle-aged people lead to an increase in arterial pressure, the development of peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum, diabetes. The combination of pathologies in patients with hypertension increases the mortality by 2.5–3 times and with type 2 diabetes mellitus by 4 times compared to the total number of the population. However, the combination of PVS and DPC with hypertension and type 2 diabetes, which are pathogenetically related and mutually burdened, complicate the diagnosis and treatment of diseases [14,18,20].

*In the structure of PVS and DPK, HR-associated forms remain dominant and make up from 70 to 88% of this pathology [3,17,18], the high virulence of which is determined by genes *cagA*, *vacA*, *uceA*, *babA*. Interesting in this aspect is the presence of toxigenic strains*

CagA, VacA, which are associated with the development of atrophic gastritis, peptic ulcer, stomach cancer, etc. [5,15,16,17,20]. Their influence leads to disruption of gastrointestinal hormones, leptin and ghrelin, glycosylated hemoglobin, which plays a major role in the development of metabolic disorders [11, 14, 19, 20].

Conclusion. Since aloe and birch buds have a wide range of medicinal properties, namely, choleric, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, anti-burn, and at the same time enhance the secretion of digestive glands, improve appetite and digestion, antibacterial property against staphylococci, streptococci, diphtheria, typhoid and of dysentery bacilli, allows establishing their influence on the course of peptic ulcer of the stomach and duodenum in combination with arterial hypertension and type 2 diabetes.

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